
Working Environment, Program Satisfaction, and Protection of Pre-Service Teachers

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ABSTRACT: This study assessed the working environment, program satisfaction, and protection of pre-service teachers of Philippine Normal University Visayas. A descriptive-correlational research method was used. A total of 203 pre-service teachers officially enrolled for off-campus for AY 2024-2025 to answer the questionnaire; only 180 responses were received. Data had been analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The study revealed that the working environment and program satisfaction of pre-service teachers were very high. The result for program satisfaction and protection of pre-service teachers is at satisfied level. A better working environment leads to higher satisfaction and productivity. Furthermore, the study revealed a significant correlation between working environment and program satisfaction. There was a significant correlation between the protection of pre-service teachers and the working environment, protection of pre-service teachers and program satisfaction. When the protection of pre-service teachers was strengthened and prioritized, satisfaction was higher. The study suggests that the protection of pre-service teachers can be addressed. Internships are the foundation of talent development, and only by enhancing the protection of pre-service teachers' motivation and the internship experience be improved, ultimately enhancing the quality of pre-service teacher development. Based on the findings, an Enhancement Program was recommended to improve the working environment, program satisfaction and protection of pre-service teachers.

KEYWORDS: Pre service teachers, program satisfaction, protection, working environment

INTRODUCTION

Pre-service teachers and students were confronted with a range of issues and concerns where their rights are treated adversely. Preparatory training in professional knowledge and skills perhaps prescribed to the pre-service teachers by a school, a higher education institution at which they are studying, or an organization. The main purpose of the internship contract, in any event, is the provision of training. This refers to a structured and supervised work experience provided to students or individuals within an educational or professional setting (Park, & Jones, 2021). It involves the application of knowledge and skills gained through academic study in a practical working environment. Internship is commonly a part of a curricular requirement or a voluntary opportunity to gain practical experience and develop professional skills. This study determined the level of the working environment and program satisfaction of the Bachelor in Physical and Health Education of pre-service teachers of PNU Visayas and explored the extent of protection and discuss how to enhance the protection of pre-service teachers. Interns is the product of the interests and needs of all parties. This practice was not unexpected, as internship programs offer considerable benefits to a variety of stakeholders including students, employers and academic institutions (Zhao,2023). During the internship, pre-service teachers and students encountered a range of issues and problems where the rights of interns were vulnerable to being treated negatively.

REVIEW OF RELATED STUDIES

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Specifically, this study will answer the following questions:

1. How may the working environment of interns be described in terms of:
 - 1.1 Working conditions?
 - 1.2 Working support?
2. What is the level of program satisfaction of interns in terms of
 - 2.1 School's internship management?
 - 2.2 School's internship guidance?
 - 2.3 Organization's internship management?

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2.4 Organization's internship guidance?

2.5 Organization's internship remuneration and subsidy policy?

3. What is the level of protection of interns perceives as pre service teachers?

4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of working environment and program satisfaction of pre service teachers?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of protection of pre service teachers and working environment?

6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of protection of the pre service teachers and program satisfaction?

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive-correlational research method was used. The aim of determining the respondents' level of the working environment, program satisfaction and protections of interns, assessing the effectiveness of internship program in the identified program of PNU Visayas. Adams & Lawrence (2019) mentioned that descriptive research collected information about the overall distribution characteristics and provides information about the overall structure, phenomena, etc. The purpose of descriptive research was to describe, explain or test hypotheses or objectives for a specific population. It was the most typically an exploration of the current status, existence and/or condition of any given topic (Miksza & Elpus, 2018).

Population and Sample

The respondents in this study were fourth-year students of PNU Visayas enrolled in their off-campus training. A total of 203 officially enrolled pre-service teachers were the respondents and only 180 responded after 4 weeks of floating the questionnaire via G form. Table A shows the distribution of respondents who answered the Survey Questionnaire for Term 2 AY 2024-2025.

Table A Number of Respondents

PNU V Curricular program	Respondent
Bachelor in English Education	33
Bachelor in Filipino Education	35
Bachelor in Math Education	25
Bachelor in Mathematics and Science	28
Elementary Education	
Bachelor in Physical & Health Education	36
Bachelor in Social Science Education	24
Total	180

Instruments

A researcher made instrument was used based from the Likert 5-point scale questionnaire on the Working Environment Scale (WES-10) Rossberg, et al (2004) Zhao (2023), Program Satisfaction Scale (PSS)), and Protection of Interns Scale (PIS-10) from Zhao (2023). First part of the questionnaire focused on basic information of the respondents. Second Part focused on the Working Environment. Third Part on Program satisfaction and the last part was the protection of pre-service teachers. SPSS statistics software for data processing and empirical testing was used.

Validity

For validity, five experts composed of program coordinators, and SASU Director were asked to review, critique and evaluate the content of the questionnaire to describe the level of working environment, satisfaction level and level of protection of the pre-service teachers of PNU Visayas. The main goal of this phase was to determine the validity of the questionnaire, where an average result of 4.49 shows a very high validity. Each category corresponds to a numerical score ranging from 1 to 5, with the scale range for each item being 0.80.

Table B Experts' Validation

No.	Validators	Scale	Interpretation
1	Validator A	4.66	Very High Validity
2	Validator B	3.33	Low Validity
3	Validator C	4.88	Very High Validity
4	Validator D	5.00	Very High Validity
5	Validator E	4.66	Very High Validity
	Average Validity	4.49	Very High Validity

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Reliability

A pilot-test was conducted to 20 Bachelor in Early Childhood Education who were able to finish their off-campus training. They are not the actual respondents of the study and securely given permission to participate in the pilot testing. The researcher used Microsoft Google form and informed the respondents to find a comfortable place as they answered the questionnaire. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used for the reliability of the instrument. The scale used a threshold of 0.70 or higher to affirm that the instrument produced stable and consistent results. The result showed an excellent result.

Table C

Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Test Result

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.95	55

When the coefficient value is greater than 0.9, the coefficient value is very good. From the above table, it can be seen that the alpha coefficient of the entire questionnaire scale is 0.95, so the reliability of this scale is very good.

Administration. The finalized questionnaire was distributed electronically using the Google form as the interns are still deployed in the different DepEd schools for their off-campus training. Clear instructions were included to guide participants through the completion process. Participants' were informed about the purpose of the study, their voluntary participation, and their right to withdraw from the study at any time. A total of 203 pre-service student was enrolled in their off-campus training during the 2nd Term for AY 2024-2025. The questionnaire was conducted online via g form. After 4 weeks the data gathered were 180 participants only. A total of 88.66 % participation. The responses of the pre-service teachers were analyzed.

Data analysis was performed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Analysis includes descriptive statistics, reliability tests, and necessary inferential statistical tests to examine the research hypotheses. Additionally, correlational analysis was used to explore relationships among different variables. For questions numbers 1, 2 and 3 Mean and standard deviation was used. For questions 4,5, & 6 Pearson Product Moment of Correlation was used in determining the correlation between the working environment and program satisfaction, the correlation between the level of protection of pre-service teachers and working environment, the correlation between the level of protection of pre-service teachers and program satisfaction.

Ethical Consideration

Participants were informed about the purpose, procedures, potential risks of the study, and the voluntary nature of their participation were fully explained to each participant prior to data collection, and they could withdraw from the study at any time without any reason. Privacy protection: Appropriate measures was applied during data processing to ensure that the confidentiality and anonymity of participants' personal information and data was protected. The form of presentation in any of the study results will not be reveal the personal identity of the participants. Conflicting Interests: The researcher does not have any financial or personal conflicts of interest that may affect the objectivity of the results in the course of this study copyright and Intellectual Property Rights: All materials used in this study (including but not limited to text, graphs, datasets, etc.) must be original or have been appropriately cited and acknowledged in the text. Compliance with laws and regulations: This study has followed the laws and regulations of the country/region in which it is conducted as well as international guidelines.

FINDINGS

Table 1.1 shows the 10 indicators of the pre-service teachers in the working environment in terms of working condition. The overall Mean of 4.61 and an SD of .52 was Very High. All mean scores fall within the "Very High" range, with values ranging from 4.42 as the lowest to 4.83 as the highest. Working Condition 1 (M = 4.83, SD = 0.43) and I understand my role in the school. (M = 4.83, SD = 0.43) received the highest ratings, signifying very high level in understanding their role in school as pre service teachers. Meanwhile, indicator no 4 on attended safety training and necessary facilities in school got the lowest with M = 4.42, SD = 1.00. The overall mean score (M = 4.61, SD = 0.51) confirms a very high level of working conditions among the pre-service teachers.

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Table 1.1 Working Environment in terms of Working Condition

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. I understand my role in the school.	4.83	.43	VH
2. I have a reasonable workload.	4.43	.76	VH
3. I have ancillary works	4.63	.64	VH
4. I have attended of safety training and necessary facilities in school.	4.42	1.00	VH
5. I feel that my workload is reasonable	4.44	.81	VH
6. I possess the ability to balance my duties in school and family time.	4.47	.73	VH
7. I understand that mental health for pre-service teacher is important.	4.80	.51	VH
8. My cooperating teacher clearly explained her/his expectations of me	4.57	.75	VH
9. My cooperating teacher helped me if I have questions on my tasks.	4.72	.73	VH
10. My assignments as pre-service teacher suits my specialization	4.76	.69	VH
As a Whole	4.61	.51	VH

Legend: 1.00-1.80 Needs Improvement (NI), 1.81-2.60Very Low (VL), 2.61-3.40 Low (L), 3.41-4.20 High (H), 4.21-5.00 Very High (VH)

This implies that the work environment in terms of working condition was perceived in Very High across various dimensions. El Salah (2021) avers that a supportive, positive and safe working environment was important to the work and career development of interns. It helped them to learn better, grow, stay healthy, build relationships, and gain real-world work experience that is critical to future career success. Consequently, employers and organizations should be committed to providing such a working environment to help interns grow. An intern with a positive working environment was more likely to have access to rich learning opportunities. This included working on various programs, obtaining mentorship and participating in trainings. These opportunities can enhance an intern's professional knowledge and skills. Schools and internships need to work together to ensure that working conditions are conducive to the development and protection of interns. Eddy, E. R., & Van DerLinden, C. (2017), Zhao (2023) averred that interns should be subject to legally mandated limits on hours of work to avoid excessive overtime or unreasonable hours of work in order to protect their rights and health.

Table 1.2 shows the descriptive statistics for the 10 indicators which shows the overall rating of 4.50 indicated Very High perceptions among the 180 respondents. Mean scores fall within the "High" range are found in indicators 1, 2, 4, 5, and 6 with mean values from 3.36 to 4.20. Meanwhile, indicators number 3,7, 8, 9, and 10 falls in the "very high level" with the mean of 4.55 to 4.82. When taken as a whole a Very High level was observed with an SD of.99. The data generally shows a very favorable view of working support among the participants. This implies that the work environment was perceived on a very high level.

Table 1.2. Working Environment in terms of Working Support

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. I have a regular job training and learning.	3.99	1.41	H
2. I attended personal career development planning and support.	3.90	1.33	H
3. I observe a positive work culture and values.	4.55	1.06	VH
4. I can talk to my fellow pre-service teachers about my problems.	3.36	1.17	H
5. I foster good relationship with my fellow pre service teachers.	3.76	1.04	H
6. I share my worries and problems with my colleagues	4.20	1.32	H
7. I support personal growth and professional activities.	4.77	1.07	VH
8. We poster good working relationship	4.82	1.03	VH
9. We support each other during school activities.	4.82	1.03	VH
10. My line of job is relevant to my pre-service specialization	4.80	1.06	VH
As a Whole	4.50	.99	VH

Legend: 1.00-1.80 Needs Improvement (NI), 1.81-2.60Very Low (VL), 2.61-3.40 Low (L), 3.41-4.20 High (H), 4.21-5.00 Very High (VH)

Juariyah et al. (2020) examined the mediating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between perceived organizational support (POS) and employee commitment. Their findings indicate that POS significantly influences job satisfaction, which in turn enhances employee commitment. Albalawi et al. (2019) explored the relationships among POS, alternative job opportunities, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover intention. The study found that organizational commitment mediates the relationship between POS and turnover intention, highlighting the importance of organizational support in retaining employees.

Linda et al. (2019) investigated the effects of perceived organizational support POS and job satisfaction on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). The study revealed that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on OCB, emphasizing the role of supportive work environments in promoting discretionary employee behaviors.

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Table 1.3 shows the working environment in terms of working condition and working support. A **Very High** level was observed among the 180 respondents. The mean score for Working Condition was 4.61 and 4.50 for Working Support, an over-all mean of 4.55 Very High. The results shows that respondents possessed high level of Working environment. This implies that the work environment in terms of working condition was perceived as Very High across various dimensions.

Table 1.3 Summary on the Description of Working Environment in terms of Working Condition and Working Support

Indicators	N	Mean	SD	VI
Working Condition	180	4.61	.51	VH
Working Support	180	4.50	.99	VH
As a whole	180	4.55	.65	VH
Valid N (listwise)	180			

Legend: 1.00-1.80 Needs Improvement (NI), 1.81-2.60 Very Low (VL), 2.61-3.40 Low (L), 3.41-4.20 High (H), 4.21-5.00 Very High (VH)

Jain and Kaur (2014), Zhao (2023) stressed that working environment is composed of three elements, the physical working environment, social working environment and mental working environment. Thus, the organization should provide a pleasant working space so that their workers can concentrate on their tasks and become more productive. Bakotic and Babic (2013) Zhao (2023) emphasized that workers who work under difficult working environment, unfriendly work mates are dissatisfied with those who work under normal working condition and in return overall performance will increase.

Table 2.1 shows the over-all mean of 3.73 which shows satisfied. Pre-service teachers are satisfied with the school internship management. Jentsch et al (2023) states that the effect of social support on teachers' job satisfaction and stress was fully mediated by teachers' self-efficacy.

2.1 The Level of Program Satisfaction of Interns In Terms of School Internship Management

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. I feel satisfied about the preparation work by the school before the internship.	3.67	.52	S
2. I feel prepared about the school's internship management system.	3.67	.51	S
3. I am prepared to handle classroom challenges and student behaviors	3.75	.49	S
4. I feel happy about the duration of the internship program.	3.77	.48	S
5. I am aware of my responsibility between the school's courses and the internship content.	3.81	.41	S
As a Whole	3.73	.39	S

Legend: 1.00-1.81 Strongly Dissatisfied ; 1.81-2.60 Dissatisfied; 2.61-3.40 Relatively Dissatisfied; 3.41-4.20 Satisfied; 4.21-5.00 Strongly Satisfied

Liang and Mo (2020) as cited by Zhao (2023) stressed that the overall student satisfaction of top-up placements was high, on satisfaction with public kindergartens significantly higher than that of private kindergartens. The work-family conflict has a positive significant effect on job satisfaction. It was noted that understanding of how work-family conflict influence job and life satisfaction in a collective cultural, as well as points to the establishment of measures to reduce work family conflict which can lead to a high level of life dissatisfaction among female prison officers (Amankwah, N. Y, et al 2025). Gomez and Tantiado (2023) claims that team work and socio emotional support are always observed and teachers are satisfied with their jobs.

Table 2.2 shows the over-all mean of 3.79 which shows satisfied. The school internship guidance also provides students with the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in a real workplace while enhancing their technical and analytical skills. Most importantly, the internship program developed students' awareness of adaptability and creativity, enabling them to adapt and respond to a changing world. Karunaratne, K, & Perera, N., (2019), Magnaye, (2022) revealed that the Student Internship Program in the Philippines (SIPP) coordinators and student interns' perception of the program implementation is effective. Alcantara (2022) conducted a study to 56 student teachers on the level of satisfaction among pre service teachers regarding their off-campus practice teaching experiences. The findings revealed a high level of satisfaction with both supports provided by student teaching office and quality internship placement.

2.2 The Level of Program Satisfaction of Interns in Terms of School Internship Guidance

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
. I feel satisfied with the guidance content provided by the schools' internship guidance	3.78	.47	S
. I feel satisfied with the guidance methods provided	3.78	.47	
. I feel contented with the frequency and timeliness of schools' internship guidance.	3.77	.47	
. I feel satisfied with the ability of the schools' internship guidance.	3.82	.45	

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. I feel confident in the attitude and support of the schools' internship guidance.	3.81	.47
As a Whole	3.79	.43

Legend: 1.00-1.81 Strongly Dissatisfied ; 1.81-2.60 Dissatisfied; 2.61-3.40 Relatively Dissatisfied; 3.41-4.20 Satisfied; 4.21-5.00 Strongly Satisfied

Table 2.3 shows the over-all mean of 3.73 which shows Satisfied. One general factor that influenced the working satisfactions such as pay and promotion, employee empowerment, psychological empowerment, remuneration, health facilities, work burden and working environment (Sun & Nyanhoka et al., 2017, Zhao, 2023). I am aware of my responsibility between the school's courses and the internship content got the highest mean while indicators number 1 and 2 got the lowest mean.

2.3 The Level of Program Satisfaction of Interns in Terms of Organization's Internship Management

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
. I feel satisfied about the preparation work by the school before the internship.	3.67	.52	S
. I feel prepared about the school's internship management system.	3.67	.51	S
. I am prepared to handle classroom challenges and student behaviors	3.75	.49	S
. I feel happy about the duration of the internship program.	3.77	.48	S
. I am aware of my responsibility between the school's courses and the internship content.	3.81	.41	S
As a Whole	3.73	.39	S

Legend: 1.00-1.81 Strongly Dissatisfied ; 1.81-2.60 Dissatisfied; 2.61-3.40 Relatively Dissatisfied; 3.41-4.20 Satisfied; 4.21-5.00 Strongly Satisfied

Table 2.4 shows the over-all mean of 3.79 with an SD of .43 which shows Satisfied. Generally, all means are Satisfied level. I feel satisfied with the ability of the schools' internship guidance got the highest mean of 3.82 with an SD of .47. While indicators number 3 I feel contented with the frequency and timeliness of schools' internship guidance got the lowest mean of 3.77 with an SD of .47. Zhao (2023) stated that many governments and university institutions around the world view internships as a cornerstone to their employability policies; in some cases, making them mandatory for graduation. Furthermore, an internship program was used to ensure that the students are prepared for their careers in a number of ways, such as gaining an understanding of the of the target career and the prospect of the target occupation and working conditions.

2.4 The Level of Program Satisfaction of Interns in Terms of Organization's internship guidance?

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
. I feel satisfied with the guidance content provided by the schools' internship guidance	3.78	.47	S
. I feel satisfied with the guidance methods provided	3.78	.47	S
. I feel contented with the frequency and timeliness of schools' internship guidance.	3.77	.47	S
. I feel satisfied with the ability of the schools' internship guidance.	3.82	.45	S
. I feel confident in the attitude and support of the schools' internship guidance.	3.81	.47	S
As a Whole	3.79	.43	S

Legend: 1.00-1.81 Strongly Dissatisfied ; 1.81-2.60 Dissatisfied; 2.61-3.40 Relatively Dissatisfied; 3.41-4.20 Satisfied; 4.21-5.00 Strongly Satisfied

Table 2.5 shows the over-all mean of 3.68 and an SD of .47 which shows satisfied. I feel satisfied with the pre-service working hours got the lowest mean on 3.61 and an SD of .66 which shows satisfied. Interns were performing valuable work tasks, an honorarium usually be provided. It was to ensure that interns were paid fairly to help cover their living costs and other expenses (Zhao, 2023). Stein (2017) stressed that interns were performing valuable work tasks, then pay should usually be provided. It was to ensure that pre-service teachers were paid fairly to help cover their living costs and other expenses.

2.5 The Level of Program Satisfaction of Interns in Terms of Organization's internship Compensation

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
I feel satisfied with the safety provision during our pre service training.	3.65	.57	S
I am happy with the arrangement of internship working hours.	3.75	.45	
I am contented with the pleasant environmental arrangement for work.	3.70	.49	
I feel satisfied with the pre service working hours.	3.61	.66	
I am satisfied with the pre-service school tasks and assignment.	3.67	.56	
As a Whole	3.68	.47	

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Legend: 1.00-1.81 Strongly Dissatisfied ; 1.81-2.60 Dissatisfied; 2.61-3.40 Relatively Dissatisfied; 3.41-4.20 Satisfied; 4.21-5.00 Strongly Satisfied

Table 2.6 shows the summary of program satisfaction of the of Interns when categorized as to identified variables, The over-all Mean was 3.74 which shows Satisfied. Zhao (2023) shared that satisfying internship experience could help interns clarify their career direction, build a professional network, and increase employment opportunities.

2.6 Summary of Program Satisfaction of Interns When Categorized as to Selected Variables

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Pre-service Internship Management	3.73	.39	S
2. School Internship Guidance	3.79	.43	S
3. Organizational Internship Management	3.72	.42	S
4. Organizational Internship Guidance	3.80	.39	S
5. Organizational Internship Compensation	3.68	.47	S
As a Whole	3.74	.36	S

Legend: 1.00-1.81 Strongly Dissatisfied ; 1.81-2.60 Dissatisfied; 2.61-3.40 Relatively Dissatisfied; 3.41-4.20 Satisfied; 4.21-5.00 Strongly Satisfied

Table 3 shows the over-all mean of 3.97 which shows satisfied. All indicators are satisfied level with the lowest mean of 3.66 and the highest mean of 4.13. Hernandez and Arrufat (2022) conducted a study on pre-service teachers' perception of data protection in primary education revealed that a high perception of risk in topics such as accepting cookies when surfing the internet or transferring banking information.

3. Perceived Level of Protection of Pre-service Teachers

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
I have clear understanding on the content of my work, working hours, and remuneration.	4.07	.60	S
I am aware of my pre service rights and relevant rights.	4.10	.59	S
I have received reasonable remuneration and benefits.	4.13	.65	S
I have enough allowances during my pre service training.	3.66	.87	S
I have been granted the prescribed rest periods during my pre service training.	3.85	.77	S
I have received timely feedback on the issues I raised during my duties as pre service teacher.	3.89	.82	S
I have received prompt assistance and solutions to the difficulties I encountered during the internship.	3.88	.86	S
I have access to a comprehensive complaint mechanism and channels during my pre service training.	3.85	.83	S
I felt assured with the support of my cooperating Teacher.	4.09	.68	S
I feel happy with the support I received from my fellow pre service teachers.	4.09	.73	S
As a Whole	3.97	.61	S

Legend: 1.00-1.81 Strongly Dissatisfied ; 1.81-2.60 Dissatisfied; 2.61-3.40 Relatively Dissatisfied; 3.41-4.20 Satisfied; 4.21-5.00 Strongly Satisfied

Makkar, N., & Kaur, M. G. (2014) stressed that the Teacher Training Programs plays a vital role in promoting Human rights among the people. The study aimed to prepare pre-service teachers and continuous in-service Teacher Education Programs that focused on Human Rights Education with an in-depth knowledge about human rights. Alderman, M. K., & Kim, J. K. (2018) expressed that schools often provide complaint channels for interns to report any violations of their rights. This helps to resolve issues in a timely manner and ensures that interns are supported and protected. Research by Wells, S. J., & Johnson, J. L. (2017) suggested that organizational internship mentoring is associated with intern satisfaction and career development because it increases interns' confidence in their work, provides opportunities to learn and grow, and thus increases their sense of advocacy. Tang and Gao (2021) avers that the relationship between the protection of intern and the satisfaction of internship programs was explored. The study

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found that protection of interns contributed to the satisfaction of the internship program and enhanced interns' professional development.

Table 4 showed the computed r value for Working Environment and Program Satisfaction of .536**. There was a significant correlation between the Working Environment and Program Satisfaction. Harrington, S. E., et al (2015) Zhao (2023) revealed that a good working environment increased interns' satisfaction and had a positive impact on their performance and career growth. The study implied that the working environment had a significant impact on interns' satisfaction. Providing a working environment that was supportive, safe, positive and with opportunities for development could help to increase their satisfaction, thus providing a more rewarding internship experience.

4. Significant Relationship Between the Level of Working Environment and Program Satisfaction of Pre Service Teachers

Variables	Computed r value	Significance (p-value)	VI
Working Environment	Program Satisfaction	.00	Sig
1. Working Condition	Program Satisfaction	.00	Sig
2. Working Support	Program Satisfaction	.00	Sig

Likewise, Taheri, R. H. et al (2020) presented that lacking of good physical conditions in the working environment would increase the dissatisfaction of interns. It meant that in order to improve the productivity and satisfaction of interns, it was necessary to pay due attention to the working environment in relation to the needs of employees. Jeske and Axtell (2019) suggested that greater working support may circumvent the sense of isolation among interns. It may specifically address increasing social connectedness within the working environment.

Generally, interns had to cope with the emotional stress associated with a new job and working environment. Working support involved providing emotional support so that interns felt that their needs and feelings were being attended to. Interns may face problems and challenges during internship. Working support can help them overcome difficulties and provide advice and resources to better perform their tasks (Zhao 2023).

5. Significant Relationship Between the Level of Protection of Pre-Service Teachers and Working Environment

Variables	Pearson R	Significance (p-value)	VI
Working Environment	Protection	.00	Sig
Working Condition	Protection	.00	Sig
Working Support	Protection	.00	

Table 5 shows the computed r value for Working Environment and Protection of pre-service teachers at .456**. There was a significant correlation between the Working Environment and protection of pre-service teachers. Alderman, M. K., & Kim, J. K. (2018), Zhao (2023) expressed that schools often provide complaint channels for interns to report any violations of their rights. This helps to resolve issues in a timely manner and ensures that interns are supported and protected. Wells, S. J., & Johnson, J. L. (2017) revealed that organizational internship mentoring is associated with intern satisfaction and career development since it increases interns' confidence in their work, offers opportunities to acquire knowledge and grow. Thus, boosts their sense of advocacy Thompson, N., & Barling, J. (2017) assessed the relationship between working conditions on the protection of interns' rights and interests. It was discovered that offering safe and reasonable working conditions and ensuring that interns are not harmed or treated unfairly on the job positively influences intern satisfaction and protection of their rights.

Table 6 showed the computed r value for Protection of pre-service teachers and program satisfaction at .468**. There was a significant correlation between Protection and Program Satisfaction of pre-service teachers. Eddy, E. R., & VanDerLinden, C. (2017) the paper considers the legal and ethical concerns of internship programs, concentrating on the protection of the rights and interests of interns in different professional fields. The influence of different fields of specialization on interns' work environment evaluations, internship satisfaction, and protection of their rights and interests is varied, as job requirements and expectations change from field to field. Internship organizations and schools should create policies in consideration of these factors to ensure the protection of rights and interests and the satisfaction of interns.

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Table 6 The significant relationship between the level of protection of the pre-service and program satisfaction

Variables		Pearson R	Significance (p-value)	VI
School's internship management	Protection	00		Sig
School's internship guidance	Protection	00		Sig
Organization's internship management	Protection	00		Sig
Organization's internship guidance	Protection	00		
Organization's internship remuneration and subsidy policy	Protection	00		

Lichtenberger, M., & Figueira, A. (2019) explored the impact of autonomous contact and uniform placement of internships, with particular attention to the impact of intern satisfaction. It was concluded that in practical management, interns' needs and organizational requirements need to be considered together to provide the best working environment, satisfaction. At the same time, a transparent protection mechanism needs to be established to ensure that the rights and of interns were protected, regardless of whether they are self-application or centrally arranged.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are made:

The Working environment of Pre-service teachers was Very High, in terms of working condition and working support and the results was very high.

The level of program satisfaction of pre-service teachers when taken as a whole was Satisfied. In terms of internship management, school internship guidance, organizational internship management, organizational internship guidance and organizational internship compensation was Satisfied.

The perceived level of protection of pre-service teachers was satisfied.

Significant relationship was observed between Working Environment and Program Satisfaction of pre-service teachers.

Significant relationship was observed between Protection and Working Environment of pre-service teachers.

Significant relationship was observed between the Protection and Program Satisfaction of pre-service teachers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. The study recommends that monitoring of working environment of pre-service teachers can be done by the supervising instructors regularly.
2. Provide guidance and support to help pre-service teachers finds suitable opportunities and ensure that the programs are relevant to their field of specialization.
3. The University can develop regulations and policies on the working environments and provide support that promote the development of the internship program.
4. For teachers that they may guide the pre-service student preparation, provide support and encourage students to share their internship experiences, communicate regularly and provide feedback for program improvement.
5. For pre-service teachers to be aware of their rights as interns and may report any infringement of their rights to their supervising instructors and he school for resolution.

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